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D6.2 – ACCEPT system prototype and integration report v1

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Executive summary

This report presents the work conducted in the iterative integration of the components specified in tasks T2.1 and T2.5.

Integration is the main focus of this document, more precisely two types of integration testing will be performed to check the specifications and functionality of the different components: automated integration testing and manual integration testing.

Independently of the type of the test, the different situations covered in the multiple tests have been described in different sections according to the use case and the business case (in each subsection of the latter one, a higher-level description of what must be tested is presented to the reader).

For each type of test, different subcategories corresponding to the ACCEPT system components will be found, with screenshots and other tests output located in the annexes where necessary to increase the clarity of the checks that have been designed and conducted.

It must be noticed that the components which have been included in an automatic testing pipeline won't appear as manually tested in the pertinent part of the document.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to iteratively (till the final version) integrate all software components of the ACCEPT system, namely the outputs of WP4/ WP5 and verify that they comply with the requirements and specifications set out in T2.1 and T2.5.

To define the different components to be tested we will use the information of the system architecture [1]. In the architecture document there are several components for which we have a description, a functional specification and a set of inputs and output. We will take each of the components and treat it as a self-contained element.

Integration of the components is done by exchanging messages and data between them. This requires that each component “understands” the messages it receives and can connect with the rest. Communication protocols were already listed on the architecture document so we will focus on the payload of the different messages. We will take the outputs that each component produces and check them against the input that the other components require.

The integration goal is to build an automatic testing platform that will ensure that the components meet the requirements for each one of the development cycles. We will test the components themselves and interacting with one another.

2. Functional testing by use case

The goal of these tests, as stated in the grant agreement, is to check that the functionality delivered by the different components conforms to what was defined in the use-case deliverable. [1]. We have also taken into account the refinement of the use cases reflected on the second architecture deliverable [2]

To achieve this, we will use the use cases themselves as a fulcrum of what needs to be tested. In this case it will not be possible to automate all the tests. Where automation is not feasible, we will do manual testing at specific points in time.

2.1. UC1 Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings.

This use case involves data monitoring and ingestion, user profiling and using the Citizen App to request data visualization. We will need to check the following items:

Scenario S01 Data Monitoring

Data from sensors is read in the BILM and sent to the ESCo Tools and then to the ECTs from there the energy community can get both IoT data and static data.

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Communication with sensors	UC1-S01-1	Yes
Data Ingestion	UC1-S01-2	Yes
ECTs request and gets data	UC1-S01-3	Yes
Energy community gets iot data	UC1-S01-4	Yes
Energy community gets static data	UC1-S01-5	Yes

Table 1. Scenario S01 Data Monitoring

For the Items UC1-S01-3, UC1-S01-4 and UC1-S01-5 (as it is show in Table 1 for the three items), the Energy Community Tools send a request to the BIML for fetching IoT and building static data and the BIML sends those data as a response. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [FT-21-01].

Scenario S02 Profile mechanism

A profile of the user is created using user data (as it is show in Table 2).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Profile is created	UC1-S02-1	Yes

Table 2. Scenario S02 Profile mechanism

Scenario S03 Data visualization (Profile)

User profile data is shown in the C-APP (as it is show in Table 3).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Profile Data is shown in the App	UC1-S03-1	Yes

Table 3. Scenario S03 Data visualization (Profile)

Manual testing by CERTH on the prototype.

Scenario S04 request for visualization (data) (see Table 4)

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
C-APP request data to BILM	UC1-S04-1	Yes
Data is shown in the App	UC1-S04-2	Yes
Data is from the correct assets/building	UC1-S04-3	Yes
Data is from the selected timeframe	UC1-S04-4	Yes

Table 4. Scenario S04 request for visualization (data)

Manual testing by CERTH on the prototype.

2.2. UC2 Building self-consumption employing Virtual Thermal Energy Storage optimization.

Scenario S01 Self-Consumption Maximization

User (Prosumer) request self-consumption optimization using C-APP and receives an optimal schedule done by ODFM using the CDT. The schedule is applied by the BILM. Results of the optimization can be seen at prosumer level (timeseries comparison).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
User request optimization (Self consumption SLA)	UC2-S01-1	Yes
Optimization performed by ODFM	UC2-S01-2	Yes
Optimal schedule is sent to BILM	UC2-S01-3	Yes
Implementation of optimal schedule by BIML	UC2-S01-4	Yes

Table 5. Scenario S01 Self-Consumption Maximization

UC2-S01-1 and UC2-S01-2 (as it is show in Table 5) manually tested by Hypertech.

For UC2-S01-3 (as it is show in Table 5): An optimal schedule for the HVAC system of the open space at the Hypertech labs. The type of messages sent to the BIML for implementation of the optimal schedule, in this case for switching on/off the HVAC system, are as follows:

`remote.control.00000SAMPLE001.C00000SAMPLE001_HVAC_1_switchBinary`

For UC2-S01-4 (as it is show in Table 5): Control actions were sent by the BAM to the BIML and the specific load implemented the control actions successfully.

2.3. UC3 Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimization taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements.

Scenario S01 Building flexibility optimization

The BAM runs a flexibility forecast optimization problem every day (day-ahead scenario) for the next day. The ODFM of the BAM runs the optimization using the trained models from the CDT. The

CDT introduces the constraints, i.e., comfort boundaries, activity patterns, etc. Flexibility is estimated.

Forecasts are sent to the ECTs upon request.

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
CDT has user data	UC3-S01-1	Yes
ODFM runs flexibility forecast with user data	UC3-S01-2	Yes
Flexibility forecast to ECT upon request	UC3-S01-3	Yes
Visualize forecast	UC3-S01-4	Yes

Table 6. Scenario S01 Building flexibility optimization

Forecast visualization (UC3-S01-4) (refer to Table 6) was tested manually by CERTH.

The BAM component requests the flexibility forecast from its ODFM sub-component, using the following:

```
// 20220914104731
// https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/lfmOrchestrator/prosumers/flexibility/forecast/9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98?period=15%20minute&startDate=2022-09-13T00:00:00.000-00:00&endDate=2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+00:00&flexibilityEstimationMethod=deltaP&baselineEstimationMethod=absoluteP
```

It should be noted that the above request is for the flexibility forecast of the Hypertech energy labs office building (under the framework of early pre-validation tests), as the ACCEPT solutions have not been deployed to prosumers at the time of writing this deliverable.

The ODFM then performs the required flexibility calculations/optimization and sends a response back to the BAM as follows (message shown in annex A using the code: [FT-31-01]:

The response (in the annex) includes values that cover all 24hours of the day for which the forecast was requested. Only a few values have been included herein for economy of space.

A similar process and message exchange is performed between the BAM and the ECTs. The ECTs may request the flexibility forecast of each prosumer by the respective BAM component using the same request.

Scenario S02 Building cost optimization

User activates cost optimization SLA from the C-APP. The ODFM of the BAM runs the optimization using the trained models from the CDT. The CDT introduces the constraints, i.e., comfort boundaries, activity patterns, etc. Control dispatch data is sent to the BAM (a summary of each step for the scenario is found in Table 7).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
User request cost optimization SLA from C-APP	UC3-S02-1	Yes
CDT has user data	UC3-S02-2	Yes
ODFM runs cost optimization with user data	UC3-S02-3	Yes
ODFM control dispatch data sent to BAM	UC3-S02-4	Yes

Table 7. Scenario S02 Building cost optimization

The result of the cost optimization performed by the ODFM can be found below:

Figure 1. Results of a cost optimisation performed by the ODFM component of the BAM

Scenario S03 Comfort as a service

User activates cost comfort SLA from the C-APP. The ODFM of the BAM runs the optimization using the trained models from the CDT. The CDT introduces the constraints, i.e., comfort boundaries, activity patterns, etc. Control dispatch data is sent to the BAM (a summary of each step in the scenario is found in Table 8).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
User request Comfort SLA from C-APP	UC3-S03-1	Yes
CDT has user data	UC3-S03-2	Yes
ODFM runs Comfort optimization with user data	UC3-S03-3	Yes
ODFM control dispatch data sent to BAM	UC3-S04-4	Yes

Table 8. Scenario S03 Comfort as a service

The result of the comfort-as-a-service optimization performed by the ODFM can be found below:

Figure 2. The output of the optimisation performed by the ODFM under S03

2.4. UC4 Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis in community level.

This UC describes elasticity estimation at community level, this elasticity is required by the Retailer Tools (part of the Energy Community tools in order to create energy tariff calculations which are used for use cases 9 and 11. Since this describes an internal process used as part of another use case check will be done in use case 9 (UC9-S01-2 and UC9-S01-3) (see Table 14).

2.5. UC5 Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management for community self-balancing.

Scenario S01 Regular Operation

ECTs send a community self-balancing request to the DAM. DAM generates forecast and generates self-balancing optimization in the storage forecasting module. DAM sends setpoints to the DIML (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 9).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
Generation forecast	UC5-S01-1	Yes
Storage forecast	UC5-S01-2	NO
Demand forecast	UC5-S01-3	Yes
DER operation data	UC5-S01-4	Yes
Control Dispatch	UC5-S01-5	Unable to test
DIML setpoints to controllable elements	UC5-S01-6	Unable to test

Table 9. Scenario S01 Regular Operation

We don't have controllable elements at this moment. We require access to controllable elements in order to test this scenario.

2.6. UC6 Day-ahead smart charging flexibility via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting.

Scenarios regarding control and usage of EV.

Scenario S01 EV availability and charging data

C-APP request EV charger data to the DIML. User visualizes data in the C-APP (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 10).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
DIML EV charger monitoring	UC6-S01-1	Unable to test
C-APP shows data to user	UC6-S01-2	Unable to test

Table 10. Scenario S01 Regular Operation

Unable to test. We don't have this kind of data in the project at this point in time. We are trying with the Switzerland demo in order to have an EV charger.

Scenario S02 EV charging profile

ECTs request data to the DAM which generates EV charge/discharge profile with DIML data (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 11).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
DIML EV charger monitoring	UC6-S02-1	Unable to test
DAM EV profiling	UC6-S02-2	Unable to test
ECT gets EV profile	UC6-S02-3	Unable to test

Table 11. Scenario S02 EV charging profile

The test concerning the retrieval of the EV profile by the ECTs cannot be performed at the time of writing this report, as there are no EVs and EV chargers available at the pilot sites. There are ongoing conversations with the Swiss pilot for the inclusion of a V2G public charger, where a shared community electric vehicle is connected.

In the case that the V2G ends up joining the trials, the corresponding integration and testing will be performed and documented in the second version of this document.

2.7. UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy.

ECT executes P2P trading requests in 15-minute intervals. The ESCo passes the request to the P2P shadow administration to manage the process. Retailer Tools generate pricing signals and the ECFM generates portfolio level optimization, with this data the P2P shadow administration calculates the P2P energy price which is used by the P2P-EP along with data coming from the DIML and the BILM executes energy/flexibility verification SCs and settlement and remuneration SCs. Finally, the P2P-EP produces P2P trading credit notifications which the user receives through the C-APP (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 12).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
ECT executes P2P trading request	UC7-S01-1	Yes
Retailer tool generates pricing signals	UC7-S01-2	Yes
ECFM generates portfolio level optimization	UC7-S01-3	Yes
P2P shadow administration calculates the P2P energy price	UC7-S01-4	Yes
P2P-EP receives IoT data from DILM	UC7-S01-5	NO
P2P-EP receives IoT data from BILM	UC7-S01-6	NO
Energy/Flexibility Smart Contract	UC7-S01-7	Yes
Settlement and Remuneration Smart Contract	UC7-S01-8	Yes
User gets P2P trading credit notification in C-APP	UC7-S01-9	NO

Table 12. UC7 Community-level P2P flexibility/energy exchange

Testing of UC7 was performed by initiating manually the flexibility and energy exchange from ECT. Mock data were used for the pricing signal and the energy production and consumption values that are generated from the Retailer Tools and the ECFM accordingly. The log files below show the result of the manual testing and the data exchange between the aforementioned components. Logs and message exchanges shown in annex A using the code: [FT-71-01].

2.8. UC8 Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes.

Scenario S01 Receive DR request

ASE (DSO_Emulator) models network behaviour and creates a DR schedule. ASE request flexibility at community level from the Aggregator Tool. ASE sends DR dispatch to the AT (depending on network state at given time). The DR event will be notified to the user via the C-APP for user agreement. Finally, the AT sends a report with the DR actions actually performed (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show inTable 13).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
ASE models network behaviour	UC8-S01-1	YES
ASE exposes DR plan on endpoint	UC8-S01-2	Yes
Aggregator request ECFM optimization for community	UC8-S01-3	Yes
ECFM request flexibility forecast for BAM and DAM and creates optimization	UC8-S01-4	Yes, partially
DR plan is used	UC8-S01-5	Yes
Aggregator activates flexibility SLA	UC8-S01-6	Yes
User receives information about flexibility in C-APP	UC8-S01-7	Unable to test

BAM executes flexibility for relevant assets	UC8-S01-8	Yes
DAM executes flexibility for relevant assets	UC8-S01-9	Unable to test
P2P-EP receives metering data and remunerates through SLA	UC8-S01-10	Yes
ASE receives verification of executed flexibility	UC8-S01-11	Yes

Table 13. Scenario S01 Receive DR request

UC8-S01-1 and UC8-S01-2 (see Table 13) testing done both through Jenkins and manually at CIRCE. Message exchanges are shown in annex A using the code: [FT-81-01].

2.9. UC9 Participation in implicit Demand Response scheme.

Scenario S01 Implicit DR

ASE creates a day-ahead pricing schedule based on actual prices (market emulator) and network status (DSO emulator). ECTs and its subcomponents RT H-ECT and DEE generate elasticity estimation and tariff calculations. This schedule is passed to the BAM for cost optimization which generates setpoints for BILM devices. BILM sends metering data to the P2P Exchange Platform in order to remunerate DR according to SLAs (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 14).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
ASE creates implicit DR schedule	UC9-S01-1	YES
Pricing information is available from the ASE	UC9-S01-2	YES
ECT generates portfolio elasticity estimation at community level	UC9-S01-3	YES
Retailer Tool generates energy tariff calculation	UC9-S01-4	YES
BAM calculates actions based on energy tariff (cost optimization)	UC9-S01-5	YES
BILM implements actions	UC9-S01-6	YES
BILM sends metering to P2P-EP	UC9-S01-7	YES
P2P-EP remunerate through SLA	UC9-S01-8	YES

Table 14. Scenario S01 Implicit DR

UC9-S01-1, UC9-S01-2, UC9-S01-3 (see Table 14) automatically tested through Jenkins and manually checked at CIRCE.

The item UC9-S01-4 (see Table 14) has already been tested under UC7-S01-2 (see Table 12).

The item UC9-S01-5 (see Table 14) is a cost optimization case, and it has already been tested under UC3 (specifically item UC3-S02-3 (see Table 7)).

The item UC9-S01-6 (see Table 14) has already been tested under UC2-S01-4 (see Table 5).

The item UC9-S01-7 (see Table 14) has returned data are the Hypertech Labs shown in annex A using code [FT-91-01].

The item UC9-S01-8 (see Table 14) has already been tested under UC7-S01-8 (see Table 12).

2.10. UC10 Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service.

Similar to UC8 and can be tested with the same test cases. The main difference is the requirements in terms of timings. This scenario requires an operation closer to near real-time and will have to be tested with synthetic data.

2.11. UC11 Retailer Day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing.

ECTs and its sub-components RT and H-ECTs use information from the ASE to build energy tariff calculations for optimal pricing. This optimal pricing is used as part of UC9 (Implicit DR) as such UC11 is tested as part of UC9 (UC9-S01-1, UC9-S01-2, UC9-S01-3, UC9-S01-4) (see Table 14).

2.12. UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management.

The DAM makes predictions on heating demand which are used by the ECT together with fuel cost data to calculate optimal schedule. ECT uses the calculated schedule to send setpoints to the DAM (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 15).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
DAM heating forecast	UC12-S01-1	NO
ECT generates optimal schedule	UC12-S01-2	Unable to test
ECT generates setpoints	UC12-S01-3	Unable to test
DAM /DIML dispatches setpoint to assets	UC12-S01-4	Unable to test

Table 15. UC12 Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management

We were unable to test this use case as we have no controllable heaters available.

2.13. UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level.

ESCo tool request to H-ECTs start of self-consumption optimization. Request flexibility forecast to the BAM and DAM. BAM requests user data to CDT. BAM requests data to BDT. BAM estimates flexibility forecast and returns it to H-ECT. H-ECT request forecast to DAM. H-ECT sends schedule to DAM. Schedules are applied and results visualized through the C-APP (a summary of each step included in the scenario is show in Table 16).

ITEM	Item Code	Item checks
C-APP request	UC13-S01-1	Yes
H-ECT request data to BAM and DAM	UC13-S02-1	Yes
BAM forecast	UC13-S03-1	Yes
DAM forecast and asset data	UC13-S04-1	Yes, partially
H-ECT self-consumption optimization	UC13-S05-1	Yes
H-ECT sends BAM optimal schedule for application	UC13-S06-1	Yes
BAM optimal schedule application	UC13-S07-1	Yes

Table 16. UC13 Increase self-consumption at community level

The item UC13-S02-1 (see Table 16) is as follows:

<https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/lfmOrchestrator/prosumers/flexibility/forecast/9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98?period=15%20minute&startDate=2022-09-13T00:00:00.000-00:00&endDate=2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+00:00&flexibilityEstimationMethod=deltaP&baselineEstimationMethod=absoluteP>

The BAM forecast response has already been provided under UC3.

The item UC13-S05-1 has returned the following:

Figure 3. Results from performance of test UC13-S05-1 by the H-ECTs.

The item UC13-S06-1 (see Table 16) has been tested and the response can be found in annex A with code [FT-131-01].

The item UC13-S07-1 (see Table 16) has already been tested under UC2 and UC4.

2.14. UC14 Active Citizen and LEC Engagement.

Nothing to test here. It describes engagement strategies not functionalities of any of the software /hardware components.

3. Functional testing by business case

This section is used to explain how the test created for the different use cases can also be used to test that the functionality of the business cases is fulfilled. We include small extracts from the business models document [3] in order to give a better context.

3.1. Business case 1

Energy Community as Flexibility Aggregator for Ancillary Service provision to System Operators and Balance Responsible Parties including network constraints management services, such as congestion management, and balancing services, such as frequency regulation.

The objective of this BC is to support the production and consumption of renewable energy by providing a solution that increases demand flexibility in order to address the issues arising from production (very variable) and demand mismatch.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use cases 8 and 10. Use cases 1, 3, 5, 6 and 11 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.2. Business case 2

Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCo) offering energy management services to community members, such as energy awareness and saving services and self-balancing on community level.

The objectives of this BC are to promote consumption of local renewable energy, to reduce the average consumption, to provide flexibility to the system and to provide information about energy market, energy production, energy prices and their forecasts.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use cases 3 and 5. Use cases 1, 2, 6, 11 and 12 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.3. Business case 3

Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCo) facilitating P2P flexibility trading (shadow administration):

The objectives of the BC are to involve community members in the management of the energy produced, to encourage consumers to reduce their consumption, to share their energy in return for payment, to enable the full exploitation of renewable energy and to reduce dependence on the grid.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 7. Use cases 1, 3, 6, 7, 8, 11 and 13 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.4. Business case 4

Energy Community as a Retailer supplying the community members with energy models and potentially participate in the wholesale market the locally aggregated energy surplus.

The objectives of the BC are to increase the forecasting skills of the system, to obtain economic benefits from energy trading and from implicit Demand Response schemes and to ensure full utilization of the clean energy produced within the community.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 8. Use cases 1, 4, 8 and 11 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.5. Business case 5

Energy Community optimized operation via P2P flexibility trading based on locally produced energy:

The objectives of the BC are to promote the consumers/prosumers to an active participation in the local energy market within the community and to increase their energy awareness. Moreover, other objective is to enable the understanding of Demand Response schemes by end-users.

Testing of this business case is covered by the testing performed for use case 7. Use cases 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 13 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.6. Business case 6

Heating-as-a-Service Provider models under schemes in which electric heating is utilized as a controllable load or alternatively through carrier coupling with DH networks leveraging the higher predictability of individual load behavior to offer heating under predefined contractual terms.

The objective of this BC is to reduce energy consumption through the replacement of the old heating system, to reduce costs for heating service and to make the end-user active in his consumption decisions.

Testing of this business case if covered by the testing performed for use case 12. Use cases 1, 2 and 4 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

3.7. Business case 7

Prosumer engagement in Implicit Demand Response for local energy profile optimization (Time-of-Use optimization):

The objective of the BC is to gain flexibility for the energy system based to the variability of consumption according to the level prices. The other objective is to reduce the energy costs for every consumer provided with this service.

Testing of this business case if covered by the testing performed for use case 9. Use cases 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 12 and 13 also contain functionality relevant to the use case.

4. Automated Integration testing

Integration testing will be done only in interfaces between components with focus on automation. The idea is that by having automated testing we can ensure integration and avoid breaking changes within the different development cycles.

The goal is to achieve this by sending request to the different components using Jenkins and checking the response against the expected result. The first step is to gather the detailed definitions of all the payloads of the communications between components. We will use this to design test request for the different interfaces.

4.1. Building Information Management Layer (BILM)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
IoT data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Weather data	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful	QUE
IoT data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Building asset static data ¹	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
IoT data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful	CERTH
Control actions	Building IoT infrastructure	JSON	RESTful	NONE

Table 17. BILM outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

We test 3 functionalities, the ability to get IoT data, the ability to get asset data and the ability to get weather data. We will not test the ability to send control actions to the infrastructure as it is not necessary for the integration (it is however necessary to fulfil the functionalities) (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 17).

- IoT data

Test run as part of the Jenkins/postman collection, we authenticate, then send a get request and get metering data in return.

- Building asset data / IoT data

Test run as part of the Jenkins postman collection, we authenticate, then send a get request and get data of the prosumer devices in return. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the codes: [IT-41-01], [IT-41-02], [IT-41-03], [IT-41-04], [IT-41-05].

- Weather data

We lack APIs to get weather data at this moment.

TEST STATUS

The test status for each item can be found in Table 18.

TEST	Status
IoT data	Passing
Building asset data / IoT data	Passing
Weather data	Not implemented

Table 18. BILM test status

4.2. District Information Management Layer (DILM)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
------	----	----------------	------------------------	-----------------

¹ Such data refer mainly to the characteristics (attributes) of building-level assets.

Format				
Control actions	Available district-level IoT infrastructure	TBD	TBD	NONE
Metering and monitoring IoT data	District Asset Manager	JSON	MQTT	CIRCE
IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	MQTT	QUE
District assets static data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	MQTT	Hypertech
EV chargers location	Citizen App	JSON	MQTT	CERTH

Table 19. DILM outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

We test 3 functionalities, the ability to get IoT data, to send district static data and the ability to get EV charger location data. We will not test the ability to send control actions to the infrastructure as it is not necessary for the integration (it is however necessary to fulfil the functionalities) (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 19).

- IoT data

Test run as part of the Jenkins/postman collection, we authenticate, then send a get request and get metering data in return. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the codes: [IT-42-01], [IT-42-02].

- static asset data

This endpoint is not built (we don't have static data)

- Weather data

This endpoint is not built (we don't have EV location data)

The test status for each item can be found in Table 20.

TEST	Status
IoT data	Passing
static asset data	Not implemented
EV chargers location	Not implemented

Table 20. DILM test status

At this point we are missing the asset static data to serve, as well as the EV chargers location (we don't have controllable EV chargers).

4.3. District Asset Manager (DAM)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	District Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Optimisation results	District Information	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

	Management Layer			
PV generation forecast	District Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

Table 21. DAM outbound messages

We test the functionality of different combinations of the two parameters presented in the table above, site and type (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 21).

The context for these tests is the one described next: these tests check if the endpoint returns the requested file depending on the project pilot and the type of forecast that the user wants to get. The site is related to who is requesting the data (partners ESR or AEM), whereas the type of forecast depends on the time rate with which the data of the forecast files was generated (the hourly forecast refers to 4 predictions every 15 minutes within the same hour. On the other hand, the daily forecast refers to 24 predictions within the same day, each of one corresponding to an hour of the day).

This endpoint uses two different parameters. Those parameters let the user choose which location (project pilot) the data will be headed to, as well as the kind of forecast that has to be obtained.

The multiple cases will be described in the following points.

- Hourly EV forecast 1

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to EV_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the electric vehicle consumption for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-02].

EV forecast is part of the optimization results as per the Architecture document (D2.4 - ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements).

- Daily EV forecast 2

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to EV_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the electric vehicle consumption for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-03].

EV forecast is part of the optimization results as per the Architecture document (D2.4 - ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements).

- Hourly PV forecast 3

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-04].

- Daily PV forecast 4

With the site parameter set to ESR and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Netherlands pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-05].

- Hourly PV forecast 5

With the site parameter set to AEM and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_hourly, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the hourly forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Switzerland pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-06].

- Daily PV forecast 6

With the site parameter set to AEM and the type parameter set to PV_forecast_daily, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds when trying to get the file corresponding to the daily forecast for the photovoltaic generation for the Switzerland pilot. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-43-07].

- Control actions

We are unable to test control actions for the DAM component as there is nothing to control.

The test status for each item can be found in Table 22.

TEST	Status
Hourly EV forecast 1	Passing
Daily EV forecast 2	Passing
Hourly PV forecast 3	Passing
Daily PV forecast 4	Passing
Hourly PV forecast 5	Passing
Daily PV forecast 6	Passing
Control Actions	Not Implemented

Table 22. DAM test status

4.4. On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	Building Information Management Layer	JSON	RESTful	QUE
Profiling data	Citizen App	JSON	RESTful	CERTH
Profiling data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Optimisation results	Energy Community Tools	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

Table 23. ODFM outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

We can't test control actions to DILM since it is not implemented. For now we test optimization results (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 23).

- Control actions

Control actions were passed from the ODFM (in fact from the integrated BAM) to the BIML and implemented by the downstream building IoT devices/loads. This has also been described under the previous chapter.

This functionality was not accessible remotely and was tested on Hypertech premises.

- Profiling data

The test of sending profiling data to the Citizen App has not yet been performed. It will be performed once devices have been installed at participating households.

The test of passing profiling data to the ECTs has been performed. Flexibility profiles calculated by the ODFM have been sent to the ECTs (through the integrated BAM component). This has been covered in the previous chapter, under UC8 for example.

This functionality was not accessible remotely and was tested on Hypertech premises.

- Optimisation results

Test run as part of the Jenkins/postman collection, we authenticate, then send a get request and get optimization results in return

The test status for each item can be found in Table 24.

TEST	Status
Optimisation results	Passing
Profiling data	Passing
Control actions	Passing

Table 24. ODFM test status

4.5. Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)

The integrated Consumer Digital Twin provides the trained models for the building and occupants to the ODFM for performing necessary optimizations. Tests performed for the ODFM on different optimisation scenarios have as a prerequisite the trained models from the CDT.

This functionality was not accessible remotely and was tested on Hypertech premises (see Table 25).

TEST	Status
Citizen Digital Twin trained models	Passing
Building Digital Twin trained models	Passing

Table 25. CDT test status

4.6. P2P Exchange platform (P2P)

Test performed manually.

4.7. Citizen Application (CAPP)

In terms of the functionality testing of the CAPP and more specifically the rest API services' responsiveness and context format correctness, we used pytest framework to develop individual scripts that guarantee the proper functionality of each sub-component. Internal algorithmic pipeline tests focus on the proper data acquisition, the algorithmic execution (time efficiency, context format).

Regarding the internal functionalities, the following table (see Table 26) displays the internal data services tests.

TEST	Status
Raw Data Visualization	Passing
Statistical Data	Passing
EV Charging Schedule	Passing
DR	Passing

Table 26. CAPP test status

Except from the internal algorithmic functionalities, CAPP interacts with external components (BIML) in order to provide NILM results.

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
NILM	BIML	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

Table 27. CAPP outbound messages

INBOUND MESSAGES

Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Status
IoT data	BIML	JSON	RESTful	NO
Optimization results	BAM	JSON	RESTful	NO
Profiling Data	BAM	JSON	RESTful	NO
DR alerts	ECTs	JSON	RESTful	NO
Pricing Data	ECTs	JSON	RESTful	NO
EV Charger's location	DIML	JSON	RESTful	NO

Table 28. CAPP inbound messages

However, it must be noted that this component version is not remotely accessible, and we have not been able to test it from CIRCE nor see interactions with other components. Nor is it able to receive data from outside sources despite it being available. In this regard the next version, planned for 30/11/2022 should be tested externally and be able to communicate with downstream components as part as its integration testing and prior to validating its functional specifications (for a summary of the messages that should be exchanged, go to Table 27 and Table 28).

4.8. Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)

The H-ECTs request flexibility data from the BAM (prosumer-level flexibility forecasts) in an automated format, using the following request:

<https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/lfmOrchestrator/prosumers/flexibility/forecast/9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98?period=15%20minute&startDate=2022-09-13T00:00:00.000-00:00&endDate=2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+00:00&flexibilityEstimationMethod=deltaP&baselineEstimationMethod=absoluteP>

The results of the flexibility forecast request are included in Annex A, under [FT-81-01].

The rest is described under the manual testing section.

4.9. ESCo Tools (ET)

No tests have been performed to date as the optimization requests sent by the ESCo tool to the C-App require that there is an active interface between the App and the ECTs. This will be tested in the next version of the report.

4.10. Aggregator Tools (AT)

INBOUND MESSAGES

Data	From	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Optimization requests	ASE	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

Table 29. AT inbound messages

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Verification of response	ASE	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

Table 30. AT outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

The ASE sends DR requests to the Aggregator tool and the response provided by the Aggregator tool is given in Annex A, under [FT-131-01] (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 29 and Table 30).

The verification of response sent to the ASE by the Aggregator toolset after the DR dispatch was tested successfully (see Table 31). Evidence of the response can be found in Annex A, under [FT-81-01].

TEST STATUS

TEST	Status
Optimisation requests	Passing
Verification of response	Passing

Table 31. AT test status

4.11. Retailer Tools (RTs)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Optimisation requests	Building Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful or AMQP	Hypertech
Optimisation requests	District Asset Manager	JSON	RESTful	CIRCE
Pricing data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	RESTful	QUE

Table 32. RTs outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

For now we test the pricing data message and the optimisation requests to the BAM (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 32).

- Pricing data
- Optimisation requests to BAM.

We send a get request for the pricing data and got a result. Additionally, an optimization request was sent to the BAM and the response was similar to the one examined under UC3.

TEST STATUS

The test status for each item can be found in Table 33.

TEST	Status
Pricing data	Passing
Optimization requests to BAM	Passing

Table 33. RTs test status

4.12. ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
------	----	----------------	------------------------	-----------------

Explicit real-time DR Request	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Explicit DR Request	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Energy prices	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech
Implicit DR Request	Energy Community Tools (Aggregator Tools, Retailer Tools and ESCo Tools)	JSON	RESTful	Hypertech

Table 34. ASE outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

For a summary of the exchanged messages, go to [Table 34](#).

- Explicit DR request (/drexplcit)

We test the functionality of different combinations of three parameters presented in the table above, date, scenario and real time.

An initial test that consists of creating the token for the next requests has been introduced. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-01].

The multiple cases will be described in the following points:

- Without any parameters, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current hour. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-02]
- With an specific date/time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-03]
- With a specific date/time parameter, scenario parameter and real time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios (real time parameter set to true). Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-04]
- With a specific scenario parameter and real time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios (real time parameter set to true). Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-05]
- With a specific date/time parameter and real time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time (real time parameter set to true). Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-06]
- With a specific date/time parameter and scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-07]
- With a specific scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-08]
- With the real time parameter set to true, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an explicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-09]

- Implicit DR Request (/drimplicit)

In this case, the token used for the requests is the same as in the previous point, so no new token creation is necessary for this step.

- Without any parameters, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current hour. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-10].
- With a specific date/time parameter and scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-11]
- With a specific date/time parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the specified date/time. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-12]

With a specific scenario parameter, the test checks if the endpoint succeeds trying to get an implicit DR scheme for the next 24 hours starting from the current date/time and the specified scenario from among a set of possible scenarios. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-13]

- Energy Prices (/pricing)

An initial test that consists of creating the token for the next requests has been introduced. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-14].

In this case, two tests have been performed to test if the API correctly recognizes the date parameter. This parameter is used to specify which time window of 24 hours the user wants to obtain.

- If no date parameter is present when the request is made (this condition represents one of the tests), the energy prices (the 24 hours of the present day) for the present day will be returned instead. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-15]
- If a date parameter is present when the request is made (this condition represents the second test for this endpoint), the API will try to get the 24 hours window time that starts at the time specified in the request. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-412-16]

TEST STATUS

The test status for each item can be found in Table 35.

TEST	Status
Explicit real-time DR Request	Passing
Explicit DR Request	Passing
Energy Prices	Passing
Implicit DR Request	Passing

Table 35. ASE test status

5. Manual Integration testing

In this section we list manual integration testing actions. The goal is to supplement testing efforts where automated testing is not feasible.

5.1. Building Information Management Layer (BILM)

Not done as all the functionalities will be tested automatically.

5.2. District Information Management Layer (DILM)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Control actions	Available district-level IoT infrastructure	TBD	TBD	NONE
Metering and monitoring IoT data	District Asset Manager	JSON	MQTT	CIRCE
IoT data	P2P Exchange Platform	JSON	MQTT	QUE
District assets static data	Energy Community Tools	JSON	MQTT	Hypertech
EV chargers location	Citizen App	JSON	MQTT	CERTH

Table 36. DILM outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

We test manually the IoT data functionality, making a get request and manually inspecting the result against the expected outcome (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 36).

- IoT data

Get request done using a testing tool. We check that the response code is 200 (ok) and manually inspect the json payload to check that it contains the expected data. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [IT-52-01].

Although this test is also performed automatically this was added as an example of manual testing.

5.3. District Asset Manager (DAM)

Not done as all the functionalities will be tested automatically.

5.4. On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM)

Tests were performed automatically.

5.5. Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)

Tests were performed automatically.

5.6. P2P Exchange platform

Regarding the P2P Exchange Platform, it was tested manually in terms of receiving market inputs from the P2P Shadow Administrator and receiving and registering a Smart Contract enabled Service Level Agreement. The latter is a Heating as Service contract between a community member and the ESCo. The following figures show the successful testing of the aforementioned functionalities.

Figure 4. Dispatch of P2P energy price from the Shadow Administrator to the P2P Exchange Platform.

Figure 5. Registering a Smart Contract on the P2P Exchange Platform.

5.7. Citizen Application (CAPP)

Manual testing on CAPP has been achieved through the Postman application or the Web app requests. Sending manual requests to specific endpoints that correspond to CAPP services in order to check that the data are well structured and include all the required content.

5.8. Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)

OUTBOUND MESSAGES

Data	To	Payload Format	Communication protocol	Destination Dev
Optimization results	P2P-EP	JSON	RESTful	QUE

Table 37. H-ECTs outbound messages

TEST DESIGN

We manually tested sending optimisation results, as well as pricing data to the P2P-EP for carrying out P2P transactions (for a summary of the exchanged messages, go to Table 37).

- Optimisation results

We sent the optimisation results generated by the ECFM of the ECTs to the P2P-EP in a JSON format. Testing evidence is shown in annex A using the code: [FT-71-01].

5.9. ESCo Tools (ET)

No tests have been performed to date as the optimization requests sent by the ESCo tool to the C-App require that there is an active interface between the App and the ECTs. This will be tested in the next version of the report.

5.10. Aggregator Tools (AT)

This was covered under the automatic testing section.

5.11. Retailer Tools (RTs)

This was covered under the automatic testing section.

5.12. ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE)

Not done as all the functionalities will be tested automatically.

6. Integration and development issues

In this section we describe which issues have caused delays in the development and integration of the solution. We also list missing functionalities as an action point to address.

6.1. Integration issues

Regarding the Citizen Application, due to the refactoring of the mock-ups and the pending communication with the rest of the relevant APIs from the side of other collaborating components that feed data to CAPP, three additional months are expected to be required, with the second and possible publicly available version being scheduled for the end of November 2022.

With regards to delays faced with the integration of the sub-components of the ACCEPT solution, these were largely since certain pivotal solution components were also delayed during their development phase. The Energy Community Tools were developed with a few months delay, so any integration testing involving communication to/from the ECTs had to also be postponed. The delay in the development of the ECTs was mainly due to further

requirements on both the back-end and front-end ECT systems received from the consortium partners and end users.

7. Integration schedule

7.1. Building Information Management Layer (BILM)

- First version done.

7.2. District Information Management Layer (DILM)

- First version done
- Second version to be planned, depending on availability of new devices from pilot sites.

7.3. District Asset Manager (DAM)

- First version done.
- Second version to be planned, depending on availability of new devices from pilot sites.

7.4. On Demand Flexibility Manager (ODFM)

- First version done.
- The second and final version of the ODFM is scheduled for the end of February 2023.

7.5. Consumer Digital Twin (CDT)

- First version done.
- The second and final version of the CDT is scheduled for the end of February 2023.

7.6. P2P Exchange platform

- First version done. However, it requires second version with shadow administrator for testability.

7.7. Citizen Application (CAPP)

- First version was abandoned due to refactoring of mock-ups.
- Second version planned for 30/11/2022.

7.8. Horizontal Energy Community Tools (H-ECTs)

- First version completed. VPP manager needs further refinement as it currently provides first-level filtering.
- The second and final version of the H-ECTs is scheduled around February or March 2023.

7.9. ESCo Tools (ET)

- First version done.
- The second and final version of the ESCo Tools is scheduled around February or March 2023.

7.10. Aggregator Tools (AT)

- First version done.
- The second and final version of the Aggregator Tools is scheduled around February or March 2023.

7.11. Retailer Tools (RTs)

- First version done.

7.12. ACCEPT solution emulator (ASE)

- First version delivered 04/07/2022 with accessible endpoints to test remotely against partner components.
- Second version delivered 15/09/2022, added real-time explicit demand response endpoint.

8. Conclusions and next steps

A research project with multiple partners makes it a challenge to create an integration schedule, as each partner has its own work methodology and timelines which might clash with the integration schedule.

In this case delays have occurred as it has not been possible to establish stable and consistent deadlines. The original goal was to have integration testing that could be done automatically to control changes and ease integration while iteratively integrating the different versions of the components. However, this kind of agile integration schedule requires an agile development schedule to match which would have required the creation of incremental testable prototypes which was not how most of the partners develop their components.

This has created a haphazard integration in which we only have been able to test that each of the components by itself fulfills the interface contracts created in the architecture document without being able to perform a top-down integration testing in which functionalities are tested from the UI down to the data received from the sensors.

The same applies to functional testing we have been able to test functionalities isolated from one another, but we have not been able to perform test while assuming the role of the user, so although we have been able to identify that the components offer the desired functionality, the system as a whole has not been tested.

Moving forward, for next versions of the deliverable all components should be accessible to test remotely either with accessible endpoints or throughout a parent component that exposes bundled functionalities of multiple components. Although integration testing should continue, as new versions emerge, focus should be on achieving top-down functional testing.

Furthermore, next versions of the deliverable will consider the final version of the architecture. In this case, the testing could not be adapted in time to take into account all the final architecture changes as the software was tested with the prior versions of the software.

9. Bibliography

- [1] "D2.1 - ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements".
- [2] "D2.4_ACCEPT system architecture description v2".
- [3] "D2.7_Report on innovative business models and service contract design v1.1".

10. Annex A

10.1. Functional testing

10.1.1. FT-21-01

The requests of the ECTs towards the BIML, for retrieving IoT and static data respectively, are as follows (UC1-S01-3):

- Request for IoT data:

```
curl -location -request GET 'https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true' \
```

- Request for static configuration data:

```
curl -location -request GET 'https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93' \
```

A sample of the responses sent by the BIML to the ECTs can be found below:

ITEM
IoT data received from a heat pump at the Hypertech labs (UC1-S01-4):
<pre>{ "_embedded": { "TimeseriesData": [{ "value": "39.079", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:29:59.999Z" }, { "value": "38.901", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:30:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:44:59.999Z" }, { "value": "39.112", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:45:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:59:59.999Z" }, { "value": "39.328", "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:00:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:14:59.999Z" }, { "value": "38.88", "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:29:59.999Z" }] }, "_links": { "self": { "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true&page=0&size=100" }, "timeseries-info": { "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93" } } }</pre>

```

},
"page": {
  "size": 100,
  "totalElements": 5,
  "totalPages": 1,
  "number": 0
}
}

```

Static configuration data from the Hypertech labs (UC1-S01-5)

```

{
  „prosumer-uuid“: „a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „prosumer-label“: „HypertechLab“,
  „prosumer-type“: „C“,
  „prosumer-country“: „GR“,
  „prosumer-global-loads“: [],
  „prosumer-spaces“: [
    {
      „space-uuid“: „1465dbd8-4393-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
      „space-label“: „LabSmallOffice“,
      „space-loads“: [
        {
          „load-uuid“: „727573ba-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
          „load-type“: „HVAC“,
          „load-label“: „Lab Central Heat Pump (ChM) (Phase 2)“,
          „load-items“: [
            {
              „item-uuid“: „e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
              „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
              „item-unit“: „W2“,
              „item-controllability“: false,
              „_links“: {
                „timeseries-data“: {
                  „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
                },
                „timeseries-info“: {
                  „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
                }
              }
            }
          ]
        },
        {
          „load-uuid“: „727573bb-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
          „load-type“: „HVAC“,
          „load-label“: „Lab Central Heat Pump (ChM) (Phase 3)“,
          „load-items“: [
            {
              „item-uuid“: „e6e10f1c-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
              „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
              „item-unit“: „W3“,
              „item-controllability“: false,
              „_links“: {
                „timeseries-data“: {
                  „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1c-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
                },
                „timeseries-info“: {

```

```

    „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1c-43ae-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
    }
  }
}
],
},
{
  „load-uuid“: „727573b9-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „load-type“: „HVAC“,
  „load-label“: „Lab Central Heat Pump (ChM) (Phase 1)“,
  „load-items“: [
    {
      „item-uuid“: „e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
      „item-metric-type“: „Power“,
      „item-unit“: „W1“,
      „item-controllability“: false,
      „_links“: {
        „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“
          „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
        },
        „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93“
          „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
        }
      }
    }
  ]
},
{
  „load-uuid“: „5f3d11b0-4459-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
  „load-type“: „SENSING“,
  „load-label“: „Ambient Sensing Antonis“,
  „load-items“: [
    {
      „item-uuid“: „5e1efba2-445a-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
      „item-metric-type“: „Motion Alarm“,
      „item-unit“: „Motion Alarm“,
      „item-controllability“: false,
      „_links“: {
        „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“
          „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/5e1efba2-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
        },
        „timeseries-info“: {
0024e84abf93“
          „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/5e1efba2-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
        }
      }
    }
  ],
  {
    „item-uuid“: „5e1efba0-445a-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
    „item-metric-type“: „Temperature“,
    „item-unit“: „Celsius“,
    „item-controllability“: false,
    „_links“: {
      „timeseries-data“: {
0024e84abf93“
        „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/5e1efba0-445a-11eb-9464-
0024e84abf93“
      },
    }
  },
}

```



```

    „item-uuid“: „166e5d78-4457-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
    „item-metric-type“: „switchBinary“,
    „item-unit“: „switchBinary“,
    „item-controllability“: true,
    „_links“: {
      „timeseries-data“: {
        „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/166e5d78-4457-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
      },
      „timeseries-info“: {
        „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/166e5d78-4457-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
      }
    }
  },
  {
    „item-uuid“: „e6491dd5-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“,
    „item-metric-type“: „Voltage“,
    „item-unit“: „V“,
    „item-controllability“: false,
    „_links“: {
      „timeseries-data“: {
        „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6491dd5-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
      },
      „timeseries-info“: {
        „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6491dd5-4456-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
      }
    }
  }
]
}
],
„_links“: {
  „prosumer-info“: {
    „href“: „https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93“
  }
}
}
}

```

10.1.2. FT-31-01

ITEM
IoT data received from a heat pump at the Hypertech labs (UC1-S01-4):
<pre> { „_embedded“: { „TimeseriesData“: [{ „value“: „39.079“, „startDate“: „2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z“, „endDate“: „2022-02-23T12:29:59.999Z“ }, { „value“: „38.901“, „startDate“: „2022-02-23T12:30:00.000Z“, „endDate“: „2022-02-23T12:44:59.999Z“ }] } } </pre>


```

        "value": "39.112",
        "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:45:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:59:59.999Z"
      },
      {
        "value": "39.328",
        "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:00:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:14:59.999Z"
      },
      {
        "value": "38.88",
        "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:15:00.000Z",
        "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:29:59.999Z"
      }
    ]
  },
  "_links": {
    "self": {
      "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true&page=0&size=100"
    },
    "timeseries-info": {
      "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/e6e10f1b-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93"
    }
  },
  "page": {
    "size": 100,
    "totalElements": 5,
    "totalPages": 1,
    "number": 0
  }
}

```

10.1.3. FT-71-01

ITEM

The Retailer tools generated the following pricing signals

```

{
  "communityUUID": "",
  "startDate": "30/09/2022",
  "horizon": "24",
  "horizonType": "hour",
  "interval": "96",
  "intervalType": "minutes",
  "signalType": "energyPrice",
  "signal": [
    {
      "value": 0.15
    },
    {
      "value": 0.15
    },
    {
      "value": 0.38
    },
    {
      "value": 0.19
    }
  ]
}

```

]
}
The energy production and consumption values that the P2P-EP requires from the ECTs have been generated as follows
<pre> { "requestInfo": { "uuid": "b9648eca-5815-44d4-9c2c-0ec4a103650d", "requestType": "explicit_production", "requestScope": "communityLevel", "communityUuid": "", "startDate": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000", "endDate": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000", "interval": "15 minutes", "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "", "baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP", "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.420+0000" }, "baselineForecasting": [{ "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000", "mean": 0.0, "unit": "kW", "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.438+0000" }, { "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000", "mean": 0.0, "unit": "kW", "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.440+0000" }, { "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:45:00.000+0000", "mean": 0.0, "unit": "kW", "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.456+0000" }, ..., { "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000", "mean": 0.0, "unit": "kW", "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000" }, { "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000", "mean": 0.0, "unit": "kW", "createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000" }] } </pre>
<pre> { "requestInfo": { "uuid": "b9648eca-5815-44d4-9c2c-0ec4a103650d", "requestType": "explicit_consumption", "requestScope": "communityLevel", </pre>

```

"communityUuid": "",
"startDate": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
"endDate": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
"interval": "15 minutes",
"flexibilityEstimationMethod": "",
"baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP",
"createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.420+0000"
},
"baselineForecasting": [
{
"dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
"dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
"mean": 980.0,
"unit": "kW",
"createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.438+0000"
},
{
"dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
"dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
"mean": 980.0,
"unit": "kW",
"createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.440+0000"
},
{
"dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
"dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:45:00.000+0000",
"mean": 980.0,
"unit": "kW",
"createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.456+0000"
},
...
{
"dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
"dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
"mean": 520.0,
"unit": "kW",
"createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000"
},
{
"dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
"dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
"mean": 520.0,
"unit": "kW",
"createdAt": "2022-09-14T07:47:31.540+0000"
}
]
}

```

The log files below show the result of the manual testing and the data exchange between the aforementioned components.

```
Market Successfully Initiated
{'start_time': 20220922000000, 'end_time': 20220922001500, 'p2p_status': 'True', 'community_id': 1001}

Requesting Energy Consumption and Production Values from ECFM...
Energy consumption and Production Values Received
{'start_time': 20220922000000, "end_time": 20220922001500, "type": "cumulative", "production": 100, "consumption": 200}

Requesting Electricity Prices from Retailer...
Electricity Prices Received
{'start_time': 20220922000000, "end_time": 20220922001500, "community_id": 1001, "price_buy": 0.07, "price_sell": 0.23}

Calculating P2P price
{'p2p_price": 0.15000000000000002, "p2p_price_buy": 0.19, "p2p_price_sell": 0.15000000000000002}
Market Completed
```

Figure 6. Log files UC7.

10.1.4. FT-81-01

The item UC8-S01-4 which refers to the request by the Energy Community Flexibility Manager of the flexibility forecasts from the BAM and the DAM to carry out the optimization has returned the following response:

```
// 20220914104731
// https://services.energylabs-ht.eu/lfmOrchestrator/prosumers/flexibility/forecast/9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98?period=15%20minute&startDate=2022-09-13T00:00:00.000-00:00&endDate=2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+00:00&flexibilityEstimationMethod=deltaP&baselineEstimationMethod=absoluteP
```

It should be noted that the above request is for the flexibility forecast of the Hypertech energy labs office building (under the framework of early pre-validation tests), as the ACCEPT solutions have not been deployed to prosumers at the time of writing this deliverable.

ITEM
Response JSON:
<pre>{ "requestInfo": { "uuid": "d3d9113c-1ee5-48be-a00e-2c977dcbd60f", "requestType": "explicit", "requestScope": "prosumerLevel", "prosumerUuid": "9d7ba727-5cbf-11ec-9d97-960000500b98", "startDate": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000", "endDate": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000", "interval": "15 minutes", "flexibilityEstimationMethod": "deltaP", "baselineEstimationMethod": "absoluteP", "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.558+0000" }, "baselineForecasting": [{ "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000", "mean": 580.2, "unit": "W", "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.580+0000" }, { "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000", "mean": 580.2, "unit": "W", "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.582+0000" }, { "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000", "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:45:00.000+0000", "mean": 3.0, </pre>

```

    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.583+0000"
  },
  ...,
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "mean": 640.4,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.671+0000"
  },
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "mean": 640.4,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.672+0000"
  }
],
"flexibilityForecasting": [
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.580+0000"
  },
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T00:15:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T00:30:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.582+0000"
  },
  ...,
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:30:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.671+0000"
  },
  {
    "dtStart": "2022-09-13T23:45:00.000+0000",
    "dtEnd": "2022-09-14T00:00:00.000+0000",
    "meanUp": 0.0,
    "meanDown": 0.0,
    "unit": "W",
    "createdAt": "2022-09-29T12:25:51.672+0000"
  }
]
}

```

The above response includes values that cover all 24hours of the day for which the forecast was requested. Only a few values have been included herein for economy of space.

A similar process and message exchange is performed between the BAM and the ECTs. The ECTs may request the flexibility forecast of each prosumer by the respective BAM component using the same request.

With regards to the verification of response, which is sent by the ECTs to the ASE, the following message is dispatched:

ITEM
Response JSON:
<pre>{ "drEventID": "report1", "communityUUID": " d3d9113c-1ee5-48be-a00e-2c977dcbd60f ", "type": "absolute", "unit": "W", "aggregatedValue": "840.9" }</pre>

The item UC8-S01-10 has already been tested in the previous section on UC7 (UC7-S01-8).
The item UC8-S01-8 has already been tested under UC2 and UC4.

10.1.5. FT-91-01

The item UC9-S01-7 has returned the following (data are from the Hypertech Labs):

ITEM
Response JSON:
<pre>{ "_embedded": { "TimeseriesData": [{ "value": "230.045", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:29:59.999Z" }, { "value": "230.581", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:30:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:44:59.999Z" }, { "value": "230.637", "startDate": "2022-02-23T12:45:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T12:59:59.999Z" }, { "value": "230.527", "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:00:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:14:59.999Z" }, { "value": "229.522", "startDate": "2022-02-23T13:15:00.000Z", "endDate": "2022-02-23T13:29:59.999Z" }] }, "_links": { "self": { </pre>

```

    "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/3cde1f48-ff56-11eb-9d63-960000500b98?startDate=2022-02-23T12:15:00.000Z&endDate=2022-02-23T13:30:00.000Z&fillGaps=true&page=0&size=100"
  },
  "timeseries-info": {
    "href": "https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/items/3cde1f48-ff56-11eb-9d63-960000500b98"
  }
},
"page": {
  "size": 100,
  "totalElements": 5,
  "totalPages": 1,
  "number": 0
}
}

```

10.1.6. FT-131-01

ITEM
Response JSON:
<pre> { "communityId": "COM01", "drEventId": 1, "drEventType": "explicit ", "startDate": "2022-12-09T13:00:00Z", "duration": "1", "durationType": "hour", "interval": "15", "intervalType": "minute", "signalType": "delta", "signalUnit": "Power", "signals":[{ "value":"+100" }, { "value:"-100" }, { "value":"+100" }, { "value:"-100" }] } </pre>

10.2. Integration testing

10.2.1. IT-52-01

DILM / district data 📄 🗑️ ⋮

Method: GET URL: <https://localhost/diml/districtdata?site=AEM> SEND

HEADERS BODY AUTHORIZATION VARIABLES

Name	Value
Authorization	ⓂJleHAI0JE2NTU0NDc4NzJ9.iek4Fsut9E0Xes-1MT7S4H-v0eBohFuEAs76E9pa4As
Name	

Response 200 OK 📄 942 B 🕒 31 ms

```

Server: nginx/1.15.8
Date: Fri, 17 Jun 2022 06:23:00 GMT
Content-Type: application/json
Content-Length: 787
Connection: keep-alive
1 {
2   "measures": [
3     {
4       "label": "DN 80 out",
5       "unit": "\u00baC",
6       "value": 88.9
7     },
8     {
9       "label": "DN 80 in",
10      "unit": "\u00baC",
11      "value": 80.1
12    },
13    {
14      "label": "Energy",
15      "unit": "kwh",
16      "value": 2293433.0
17    },
18    {
19      "label": "Power",
20      "unit": "kW",
21      "value": 459.6
22    },
23    {
24      "label": "volume",
25      "unit": "m3/h",

```

10.2.2. IT-41-01, User authentication

Iteration: 1 - User authentication

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: **POST**
- Request URL: <https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/auth>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: **200 - OK**
- Mean time per request: **355ms**
- Mean size per request: **2.29KB**

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	b95c7fc7-76a3-4e26-b12a-4252a3baa997
Host	projects.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	35

RESPONSE HEADERS	
Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:15:15 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2350
Connection	keep-alive
Cache-Control	no-store
Set-Cookie	KEYCLOAK_LOCALE=en; Version=1; Path=/auth/realms/fiml-projects/; Secure; HttpOnly
Set-Cookie	KC_RESTART=; Version=1; Expires=Thu, 01-Jan-1970 00:00:10 GMT; Max-Age=0; Path=/auth/realms/fiml-projects/; HttpOnly
X-XSS-Protection	1; mode=block
Pragma	no-cache
X-Frame-Options	SAMEORIGIN
Referrer-Policy	no-referrer
Strict-Transport-Security	max-age=31536000; includeSubDomains
X-Content-Type-Options	nosniff

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED],
  "expires_in": 3600,
  "refresh_expires_in": 2592000,
  "refresh_token": [REDACTED],
  "token_type": [REDACTED],
  "not-before-policy": 1649348617,
  "session_state": "1a8e21a7-ab1e-43cf-abb1-5d94956f504a",
  "scope": "PilotPartnerAttributes"
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T1	Passed	T1	Failed	T1	Skipped	T1
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.3. IT-41-02, Prosumer configuration

Iteration: 1 - Prosumer configuration

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 312ms
- Mean size per request:** 312.7KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	b26d2d30-26b0-4301-9376-b9d122a4f3d7
Host	projects.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:15:15 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "_embedded": {
    "prosumerConfigurationList": [
      {
        "prosumer-uuid": "a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
        "prosumer-label": "HypertechLab",
        "prosumer-type": "C",
        "prosumer-country": "GR",
        "prosumer-global-loads": [],
        "prosumer-spaces": [
          {
            "space-uuid": "1465dbd8-4393-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
            "space-label": "LabSmallOffice",
            "space-loads": [
              {
                "load-uuid": "727573ba-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.4. IT-41-03, Load configuration

Iteration: 1 - Prosumer - Load configuration

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93/////////>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 93ms
- Mean size per request:** 122.46KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	960e8c78-cf0e-46b4-9672-7a9e2172f3cc
Host	projects.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:15:16 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "prosumer-uuid": "a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
  "prosumer-label": "HypertechLab",
  "prosumer-type": "C",
  "prosumer-country": "GR",
  "prosumer-global-loads": [],
  "prosumer-spaces": [
    {
      "space-uuid": "1465dbd8-4393-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
      "space-label": "LabSmallOffice",
      "space-loads": [
        {
          "load-uuid": "727573ba-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
          "load-type": "HVAC",
          "load-label": "Lab Central Heat Pump (CHP) (Phase 2)",
          "load-items": [

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.5. IT-41-04, Building configuration

Iteration: 1 - Prosumer - Building configuration

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/prosumers/a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 79ms
- Mean size per request:** 97.31KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	2de3b1c6-1f09-4298-b0fb-464e91f076b0
Host	projects.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.14.0 (Ubuntu)
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:15:16 GMT
Content-Type	application/hal+json
Transfer-Encoding	chunked
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "prosumer-uuid": "a9446cdb-438f-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
  "prosumer-label": "HypertechLab",
  "prosumer-type": "C",
  "prosumer-country": "GR",
  "prosumer-global-loads": [],
  "prosumer-spaces": [
    {
      "space-uuid": "1465dbd8-4393-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
      "space-label": "LabSmallOffice",
      "space-loads": [
        {
          "load-uuid": "727573ba-43ad-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93",
          "load-type": "HVAC",
          "load-label": "Lab Central Heat Pump (CHP) (Phase 2)",
          "load-items": [

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.6. IT-41-05, 1 data retrieval

Iteration: 1 - Item -1 data retrieval

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: GET
- i Request URL: <https://projects.energylabs-ht.eu/api/data/e6e10f1a-43ae-11eb-9464-0024e84abf93?startDate=2022-06-08T00:00:00.000Z&endDate=2022-06-09T00:00:00.000Z>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 2s
- i Mean size per request: 5KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	11d44925-847b-49cd-8c09-ef8d03f3ba1c
Host	projects.energylabs-ht.eu
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

"endDate": "2022-06-08T03:29:59.999Z"
},
{
  "value": "982.609",
  "startDate": "2022-06-08T06:45:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "2022-06-08T06:59:59.999Z"
},
{
  "value": "989.506",
  "startDate": "2022-06-08T07:00:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "2022-06-08T07:14:59.999Z"
},
{
  "value": "1038.571",
  "startDate": "2022-06-08T07:15:00.000Z",
  "endDate": "2022-06-08T07:29:59.999Z"
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.7. IT-42-01, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: POST
- i Request URL: <https://192.168.30.2/diml/token>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 125ms
- i Mean size per request: 278B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	2bd9b86d-6369-4d5d-9a40-1d440682e820
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	59

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 05:03:01 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	278
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.8. IT-42-02, District data

Iteration: 1 - District data

REQUEST INFORMATION

- i Request Method: GET
- i Request URL: <https://192.168.30.2/diml/districtdata?site=AEM>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- i Response Code: 200 - OK
- i Mean time per request: 10ms
- i Mean size per request: 787B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	597b33a3-5f4a-4d23-a4f4-9282ef01f19f
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 05:03:01 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	787
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "measures": [
    {
      "label": "DN 80 out",
      "unit": "°C",
      "value": 88.9
    },
    {
      "label": "DN 80 in",
      "unit": "°C",
      "value": 88.1
    },
    {
      "label": "Energy",
      "unit": "kWh",
      "value": 2293433
    }
  ]
}
        
```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.9. IT-43-01, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - Create token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/token>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 225ms
- Mean size per request:** 278B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	7ee33778-5ad2-4a2d-bce7-f68380d47075
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	59

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "username": "devC1rce",
  "password": "J1NT8gedtW3hokPQ7hrs"
}

```

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RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:01 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	278
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.10. IT-43-02, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and EV_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = EV_forecast_hourly)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=EV_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 35ms
- Mean size per request:** 536B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	a3f12f25-b68a-4b25-9e93-58bb3bdb3c7a
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	536
Connection	keep-alive

10.2.11. IT-43-03, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and EV_forecast_daily as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = EV_forecast_daily) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=EV_forecast_daily

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 37ms
- Mean size per request:** 2.32KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	828d0134-e569-40e6-9aad-09874f41be2e
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2375
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2022-10-05",
  "Demo_id": "NED",
  "Asset_name": "EV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "23:49:06.308888",
      "Value [kw]": 0.281
    },
    {
      "Time": "00:49:06.308888",
      "Value [kw]": 0.266
    },
    {
      "Time": "01:49:06.308888",
      "Value [kw]": 0.251
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

10.2.12. IT-43-04, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and PV_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = PV_forecast_hourly)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=PV_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 33ms
- Mean size per request:** 568B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	6711cdf2-9dac-418c-acbe-a55397c91fd7
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	568
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2022-10-06",
  "Demo:Id": "NEB",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 02:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 02:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 02:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 02:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 03:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 03:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 03:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 03:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 04:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 04:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 04:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 04:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 05:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 05:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 05:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 05:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 06:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 06:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 06:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 06:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 07:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 07:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 07:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 07:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 08:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 08:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 08:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 08:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 09:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 09:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 09:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 09:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 10:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 10:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 10:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 10:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 11:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 11:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 11:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 11:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 12:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 12:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 12:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 12:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 13:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 13:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 13:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 13:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 14:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 14:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 14:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 14:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 15:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 15:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 15:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 15:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 16:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 16:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 16:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 16:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 17:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 17:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 17:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 17:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 18:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 18:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 18:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 18:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 19:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 19:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 19:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 19:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 20:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 20:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 20:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 20:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 21:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 21:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 21:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 21:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 22:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 22:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 22:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 22:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 23:00:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 23:15:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 23:30:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 23:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
contains data	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0

10.2.13. IT-43-05, Get data (with ESR as site parameter and PV_forecast_daily as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = ESR and type = PV_forecast_daily) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=ESR&type=PV_forecast_daily

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 34ms
- Mean size per request:** 2.54KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	f3e51f6a-732f-4099-82cf-6dc030c69524
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2596
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2022-10-06",
  "Demo:Id": "NED",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kw]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 02:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kw]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 03:45:13+02:00",
      "Value [kw]": 0
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
contains data	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0

10.2.14. IT-43-06, Get data (with AEM as site parameter and PV_forecast_hourly as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = AEM and type = PV_forecast_hourly)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=AEM&type=PV_forecast_hourly

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 34ms
- Mean size per request:** 568B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	a4c9add2-7547-4968-a27c-c31ebcace421
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	568
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2022-10-06",
  "Demo:Id": "SUI",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:04:06+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:19:06+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    }
  ]
}

```

TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

10.2.15. IT-43-07, Get data (with AEM as site parameter and PV_forecast_daily as type parameter)

Iteration: 1 - Get data (site = AEM and type = PV_forecast_daily) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** https://accept.fcirce.es/dam/damdata?site=AEM&type=PV_forecast_daily

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 33ms
- Mean size per request:** 2.53KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	44eeb195-17db-4651-90a7-d7186bcb952
Host	20.216.174.110
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:57:02 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	2595
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "Date": "2022-10-06",
  "Demo: id": "SUI",
  "Asset_name": "PV",
  "Data": "Day-Ahead Generation Forecast",
  "Data_Type": "Array",
  "Values": [
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 01:49:06+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {
      "Time": "2022-10-07 02:49:06+02:00",
      "Value [kW]": 0
    },
    {

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
contains data	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0

10.2.16. IT-412-01, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** POST
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/token>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 219ms
- Mean size per request:** 278B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	c7460010-ebd2-4ea2-aebc-65a131b00b44
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	59

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "username": "devC1rce",
  "password": "J1nT8qeGbu3hokPQ7hrs"
}

```

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RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	278
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.17. IT-412-02, Explicit demand response

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: GET
- Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: 200 - OK
- Mean time per request: 38ms
- Mean size per request: 1.56KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	b84e906f-45af-4ba5-a07e-70a7baff8150
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1611
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 08:51:37",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": -9576.471000000005
    },
    {
      "value": -9576.471000000005
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓ Passed	↑↓ Failed	↑↓ Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.18. IT-412-03, Explicit demand response with date parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 37ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.54KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE
100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	e4a3b43c-e799-43ad-b692-4a68a2511969
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1581
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": -9576.471000000005
    },
    {
      "value": -2733.3333333333335
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓ Passed	↑↓ Failed	↑↓ Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.19.IT-412-04, Explicit demand response with date parameter, scenario parameter and real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date, scenario and real time (true) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&realtime=1&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 33ms
- Mean size per request:** 284B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	6da5d26d-1f0a-4957-b4b7-6c277a5827ac
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	283
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.20. IT-412-05, Explicit demand response with scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 35ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.62KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE
100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	31157690-67d4-4082-9a16-8fbcdcf38102
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1668
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 08:51:37",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 6557.8599999999996
    },
    {
      "value": 737.9192499999999
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	1	0	0

10.2.21. IT-412-06, Explicit demand response with real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit real time (true)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?realtime=1>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 34ms
- Mean size per request:** 284B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	42e4922c-c3fd-4cfa-a9f4-ba038195f136
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	284
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "explicit realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 08:51:37",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T1	Passed	T1	Failed	T1	Skipped	T1
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.22. IT-412-07, Explicit demand response with date parameter and real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date and real time (true) ▼

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&realtime=1&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 35ms
- Mean size per request:** 283B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	efc03cf-2a07-4d2b-b226-e4f4e4521d75
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	283
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit_realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name		Passed		Failed		Skipped	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.23. IT-412-08, Explicit demand response with date parameter and scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit date and scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 36ms
- Mean size per request:** 1.62KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	421f1b74-84d2-44ca-afab-3223ad920b33
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1659
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 1167.273999999995
    },
    {
      "value": 1167.273999999995
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.24. IT-412-09, Explicit demand response with scenario parameter and real time parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR explicit scenario and real time (true)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drexplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&realtime=1&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 38ms
- Mean size per request:** 283B

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	efc03cf-2a07-4d2b-b226-e4f4e4521d75
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	283
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```
{
  "scenario": "sc0101",
  "drEventType": "explicit realtime",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 15,
  "durationType": "minute",
  "interval": 15,
  "interval_type": "minute",
  "signalType": "delta",
  "signalUnit": "Power",
  "signals": 0
}
```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T1	Passed	T1	Failed	T1	Skipped	T1
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.25. IT-412-10, Implicit demand response

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: GET
- Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimplicit>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: 200 - OK
- Mean time per request: 70ms
- Mean size per request: 4.72KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	e54eb176-9127-4160-802e-6b7d8b05fa63
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:37 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	5052
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "implicit",
  "startDate": "2022-10-24 00:51:37",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "absolute",
  "signalUnit": "euro",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 101.94061199999999
    },
    {
      "value": 100.504744
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.26. IT-412-11, Implicit demand response with date parameter and scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit date and scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimPLICIT?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00&scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 70ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.72KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE
100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	93cfb536-da15-4098-aa30-01221202cc8d
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:38 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	4829
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "sce101",
  "drEventType": "implicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "absolute",
  "signalUnit": "euro",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 185.25
    },
    {
      "value": 184.24
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.27. IT-412-12, Implicit demand response with date parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit date

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimplicit?date=2022-06-12%2000:00:00>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 70ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.73KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	da858174-e953-4d14-a06e-863e0d49818d
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:38 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	4841
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "scenario": "default",
  "drEventType": "implicit",
  "startDate": "2022-06-12 00:00:00",
  "duration": 24,
  "durationType": "hour",
  "interval": 1,
  "interval_type": "hour",
  "signalType": "absolute",
  "signalUnit": "euro",
  "signals": [
    {
      "value": 241.75
    },
    {
      "value": 211.876
    }
  ]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.28. IT-412-13, Implicit demand response with scenario parameter

Iteration: 1 - DR implicit scenario

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method:** GET
- Request URL:** <https://accept.fcirce.es/dso/drimplicit?scenario=sc0101>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code:** 200 - OK
- Mean time per request:** 68ms
- Mean size per request:** 4.72KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	[REDACTED]
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	60c5da96-4efe-4b05-8c0c-c27bcf81c4d0
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 06:51:38 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	5067
Connection	keep-alive

10.2.29. IT-412-14, Token creation

Iteration: 1 - Create token

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: **POST**
- Request URL: https://accept.fcirce.es/market/create_token

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: **200 - OK**
- Mean time per request: **219ms**
- Mean size per request: **2768**

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	57d046b6-967f-4708-bbb9-d068f82046a1
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	69

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "username": "training",
  "password": "Arqch[0r&+?^2k]8"
}

```

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RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:40:28 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	276
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "access_token": [REDACTED]
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	T1	Passed	T1	Failed	T1	Skipped	T1
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		1		0		0	

10.2.30.IT-412-15, Energy prices retrieval for a specific date

Iteration: 1 - Get_data

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: GET
- Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/market/pricing>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: 200 - OK
- Mean time per request: 58ms
- Mean size per request: 1.01KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	1f06063d-b592-417a-97b8-7fecc00bad90
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	49

REQUEST BODY

```

{
  "year": 2022,
  "month": 6,
  "day": 8,
  "hour": 13
}

```

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RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:40:29 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1032
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "data": {
    "2022-10-24 10:00:00": 88.507195,
    "2022-10-24 11:00:00": 85.81104,
    "2022-10-24 12:00:00": 79.48544,
    "2022-10-24 13:00:00": 74.041725,
    "2022-10-24 14:00:00": 58.94369,
    "2022-10-24 15:00:00": 53.660236,
    "2022-10-24 16:00:00": 54.07508,
    "2022-10-24 17:00:00": 77.7997,
    "2022-10-24 18:00:00": 85.224625,
    "2022-10-24 19:00:00": 106.338844,
    "2022-10-24 20:00:00": 128.02188,
    "2022-10-24 21:00:00": 121.67363,
    "2022-10-24 22:00:00": 111.38073,
    "2022-10-24 23:00:00": 99.335075,
    "2022-10-24 00:00:00": 87.771775
  }
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	↑↓	Passed	↑↓	Failed	↑↓	Skipped	↑↓
contains data		1		0		0	
Status code is 200		1		0		0	
Total		2		0		0	

10.2.31. IT-412-16, Energy prices retrieval for today's date

Iteration: 1 - Get_data (empty json body)

REQUEST INFORMATION

- Request Method: GET
- Request URL: <https://accept.fcirce.es/market/pricing>

RESPONSE INFORMATION

- Response Code: 200 - OK
- Mean time per request: 67ms
- Mean size per request: 1.01KB

TEST PASS PERCENTAGE

100 %

REQUEST HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Authorization	
Content-Type	application/json
User-Agent	PostmanRuntime/7.29.0
Accept	*/*
Cache-Control	no-cache
Postman-Token	4a5d3ab0-e6eb-4b10-a63f-f4ecc1b1f5e8
Host	accept.fcirce.es
Accept-Encoding	gzip, deflate, br
Connection	keep-alive
Content-Length	2

REQUEST BODY

```
{}

```

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RESPONSE HEADERS

Header Name	Header Value
Server	nginx/1.15.8
Date	Mon, 24 Oct 2022 09:40:29 GMT
Content-Type	application/json
Content-Length	1032
Connection	keep-alive

RESPONSE BODY

```

{
  "data": {
    "2022-10-24 10:00:00": 88.507195,
    "2022-10-24 11:00:00": 85.81184,
    "2022-10-24 12:00:00": 79.48544,
    "2022-10-24 13:00:00": 74.841725,
    "2022-10-24 14:00:00": 58.94369,
    "2022-10-24 15:00:00": 53.668236,
    "2022-10-24 16:00:00": 54.87588,
    "2022-10-24 17:00:00": 77.7997,
    "2022-10-24 18:00:00": 85.224625,
    "2022-10-24 19:00:00": 100.338844,
    "2022-10-24 20:00:00": 128.82188,
    "2022-10-24 21:00:00": 121.67363,
    "2022-10-24 22:00:00": 111.38875,
    "2022-10-24 23:00:00": 98.338075,
  }
}

```

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TEST INFORMATION

Search:

Name	Passed	Failed	Skipped
contains data	1	0	0
Status code is 200	1	0	0
Total	2	0	0